

Reyna

INTERESTED IN FAMILY HISTORY, 25

Boston (USA)
Degree in Economics

EXPERIENCE WITH BIOGRAPHICAL DATA

Unaware	Reluctant	Limited	Confident

GOALS RELATED TO DH RESEARCH

1.
2.
3.

CHALLENGES RELATED TO DH RESEARCH

1.
2.
3.

BEHAVIOR MATRIX

CERTAINTY WHEN DOING RESEARCH	high	
	none	high
	DEPTH OF USING PERSONAL DATA	

*“In relation to Digital Humanities, Reyna wishes to
.....
.....
.....”*

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Carlos

DIGITAL HUMANITIES STUDENT, 20

Valencia (Spain)

Third Year College Student

EXPERIENCE WITH BIOGRAPHICAL DATA

Unaware	Reluctant	Limited	Confident

GOALS RELATED TO DH RESEARCH

1.
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CHALLENGES RELATED TO DH RESEARCH

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BEHAVIOR MATRIX

CERTAINTY WHEN DOING RESEARCH	high	
	none	high
	DEPTH OF USING PERSONAL DATA	

*“In relation to Digital Humanities, Carlos wishes to
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.....”*

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Paul

HISTORY TEACHER, 47

Manchester (UK)
King David High School

EXPERIENCE WITH BIOGRAPHICAL DATA

Unaware	Reluctant	Limited	Confident

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BEHAVIOR MATRIX

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"In relation to Digital Humanities, Paul wishes to
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Lis

WIKIMEDIAN IN RESIDENCE, 30

Berlin (Germany)

Deutsche Nationalbibliothek

EXPERIENCE WITH BIOGRAPHICAL DATA

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Maria

MUSEUM CURATOR, 50

São Paulo (Brasil)

São Paulo Museum of Modern Art

EXPERIENCE WITH BIOGRAPHICAL DATA

Unaware	Reluctant	Limited	Confident

GOALS RELATED TO DH RESEARCH

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CHALLENGES RELATED TO DH RESEARCH

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CERTAINTY WHEN DOING RESEARCH	high	
	none	high
	DEPTH OF USING PERSONAL DATA	

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Veena

DIGITAL HUMANITIES RESEARCHER, 38

Punjab (India)

Postdoctoral Fellow at University of Chicago

EXPERIENCE WITH BIOGRAPHICAL DATA

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"In relation to Digital Humanities, Veena wishes to
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Abasi

DATA SCIENTIST, 35

Cairo (Egypt)

Institut Français d'Archéologie Orientale du Caire

EXPERIENCE WITH BIOGRAPHICAL DATA

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Steve

PHD CANDIDATE, 35

Toronto (Canada)

University of Toronto, Department of Political Science

EXPERIENCE WITH BIOGRAPHICAL DATA

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